

Feature Article**ECOLOGY AND EPIDEMIOLOGY OF DISEASES OF NUT CROPS AND OLIVES
CAUSED BY BOTRYOSPHAERIACEAE FUNGI IN CALIFORNIA AND SPAIN**

Page | 1

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ABSTRACT

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In recent decades, the cultivated area and production of nuts and olives have increased, driven by an increasing consumer interest in healthier food. Diseases of almond, pistachio, olive, and walnut crops caused by species belonging to the Botryosphaeriaceae family have caused concern worldwide. Although considerable progress has been made in elucidating the etiology of these diseases, scientific knowledge of other aspects of these diseases is more limited. In this article, we present an overview of the most important diseases caused by Botryosphaeriaceae fungi affecting almond, pistachio, olive, and walnut crops by focusing on ecology and epidemiology, primarily in California and Spain.

Additional Keywords: *Botryosphaeria*, *Neofusicoccum*, canker, blight, fruit rot, escudete

Nut fruits, including almond, pistachio, and walnut, and olive oil, are essential foods of a healthy Mediterranean diet (Estruch et al. 2013). Beneficial effects of consuming nuts and olives include reduction of metabolic syndrome and a lower risk for cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes (Kris-Etherton et al. 2007).

18 Consumers' heightened interest in nutritional aspects of food during recent decades has led to
19 a substantial increase in the worldwide production of almond, pistachio, and walnut. Almond,
20 pistachio, and walnut production worldwide rose from 2,731 to 3,571 metric tons from 2010-
21 11 to 2015-16. During this period, California produced around 45% of pistachio, walnut, and
22 almond crops (Figs. 1A-C); it remains the world leader in almond production. Currently, Spain
23 is ranked as the third almond producer worldwide with 53 metric tons after USA and Australia
24 but is ranked first in almond-growing area with 540,000 ha (www.magrama.gob.es).
25 This discrepancy between output and production area is due to fact that most Spanish almond
26 orchards have poor soils, depend on rain for irrigation, and consist of traditional, early-
27 flowering, relatively low-yielding cultivars (Fig. 1D). Because almond orchards are more
28 profitable than olive orchards, almond production is increasing, while olive production is stable
29 in traditional olive-growing regions of Spain (D. Barranco, *personal communication*). The
30 economic and social importance of olive is enormous in Spain, and it is the worldwide leader
31 with more than 2.5 million hectares (Figs. 1E-F) and economic value of \$2.4 billion
32 (www.magrama.gob.es).

33 Cankers caused by species in the fungal family Botryosphaeriaceae are a major constraint to
34 production of almond, pistachio, walnut (these three crops are collectively referred to as nut
35 crops in this article), and olive. In general, these pathogens infect lignified tissues and, less
36 frequently, fruit, leaves, and flowers (Teviotdale et al. 2011; Trapero et al. 2011). Reviewing
37 the output of *Botryosphaeria* articles in APS journals, we noted that disease etiology,
38 epidemiology/ecology, and control/resistance were addressed relatively equally until 2004,
39 after which articles about etiology increased more than the other two types (Fig. 2). In this
40 article, we review the current situation of the ecology and epidemiology of Botryosphaeriaceae
41 species affecting almond, pistachio, olive, and walnut crops under Mediterranean conditions.

42 **Taxonomy and description of the diseases**

43 ***Botryosphaeriaceae* family**

44 Botryosphaeriaceae is a large family of filamentous fungi in the Ascomycota whose first
45 members were described in the 1820s as species of *Sphaeria* (Fries) (Phillips et al. 2013;
46 Slippers et al. 2013). Cesati and De Notaris (1863) established the genus *Botryosphaeria*
47 including 12 species in the second half of the 19th century. Theissen and Sydow (1918)
48 introduced the Botryosphaeriaceae as a sub-family in the Pseudosphaeriaceae family. Major
49 taxonomic diversification within the family during the first half of the 20th century was

50 reviewed by Von Arx and Muller (1954). Currently, Botryosphaeriaceae encompasses 17
51 genera, of which *Botryosphaeria*, *Diplodia*, *Dothiorella*, *Lasiodiplodia*, *Neofusicoccum*,
52 *Neoscytalidium*, and *Macrophomina* have been described as pathogens on nut crops or olive
53 (Chen et al. 2014b; Gramaje et al. 2012; Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Phillips et al. 2013; Urbez-
54 Torres et al. 2013). Botryosphaeriaceae species show uni- to multilocular ascomata, occurring
55 singly or in clusters; asci are bitunicate and clavate; ascospores can be hyaline or colored, and
56 aseptate or 1-2-septate. Conidia can be hyaline and narrow or wide (called fusicoccum-like or
57 diplodia-like, respectively), but colored conidia can be found in some species. Species in
58 *Neoscytalidium* also produce arthrospores in chains as mature mycelia break into pieces
59 (Phillips et al. 2013; Slippers et al. 2013). Morphological characteristics of conidia and colonies
60 have been traditionally used for indentifying Botryosphaeriaceae species affecting woody
61 crops (English 1975; Michailides 1991; Romero et al. 2005). More recently, however, the
62 morphologically based concept of species was displaced by the phylogenetic concept of
63 species, which incorporates DNA sequence homology and phylogenetic analysis and has
64 uncovered multiple cryptic species that originally belonged to a single morphological species
65 (Taylor et al. 2000).

66 The phylogenetic approach has provided significant taxonomic changes during the last decade.
67 The genus *Botryosphaeria* now includes *B. agaves*, *B. corticis*, *B. dothidea*, *B. fabricerciana*,
68 *B. fusispora*, *B. ramose*, and *B. scharifii* (Phillips et al. 2013; Slipper et al. 2013). Interestingly,
69 *B. dothidea*, which was considered the only species associated with panicle and shoot blight of
70 pistachio for 10 years (Michailides 1991; Smith et al. 2001), is now considered a secondary
71 pathogen in this host, whereas *Neof. mediterraneum* seems to be the main pathogen (Chen et
72 al. 2014a; Moral et al. 2010). In general, *Botryosphaeria* species affecting nut crops and olives
73 are nonobligate parasites that have a worldwide distribution. They can attack more than 150
74 species including angiosperms (both monocotyledonous and dicotyledonous) and
75 gymnosperms. From an ecological point of view, Botryosphaeriaceae species have long been
76 known as pathogens, saprophytes, and endophytes (Slippers and Wingfield 2007).

77 **Symptomatology, economic importance, and etiology**

78 ***Almond***

79 A canker disease of almond trunk and scaffold branches caused by *B. dothidea* was described
80 in California in the mid-1950s (English 1975). The pathogen kills the bark of almonds, causing
81 a canker that expands horizontally in the tree trunk, forming a band that appears recessed

82 (English 1975; Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Figs. 3A-B), resulting in the common name “band
83 canker”. Infection occurs through natural growth cracks in the bark caused by trunk growth.
84 For this reason, symptoms often appear in 3- to 5-year-old trees on vigorous hybrid rootstocks.
85 The pathogen, initially identified as *B. dothidea*, was reported to cause cankers of branches,
86 shoots, and twigs of almond – so-called “canopy cankers” - in the 1980s. During the next
87 decade, we also found cankers with exuding sap, a characteristic sign of cankers on this crop,
88 around pruning wounds on almond branches (Michailides et al. 2018). Infections of trunk or
89 scaffold branches can lead to initial wilting, thin canopy, chlorotic foliage, and gradual decline.
90 Infection by Botryosphaeriaceae species can often cause the loss of the tree when the canker
91 encircles the trunk. Moreover, severely affected trees are subject to breakage due to wind or
92 harvesting. More rarely, cankers are formed in areas of the branches that bear nuts causing the
93 blight of fruit with or without gumming (Figs. 3C-D).

Page | 4

94 In California, almond band canker was sporadic until the first years of the present century,
95 when numerous severe outbreaks were reported (Michailides et al. 2009; 2018). In Merced
96 County, four orchards showed 15.8% of almonds with typical disease symptoms (Doll et al.
97 2013). In Mallorca Island, Spain, prevalence of Botryosphaeriaceae pathogens in almond
98 orchards is around 40% but associated with branch dieback rather than the band canker symptom
99 (Olmo 2015). Californian almond nurseries have also experienced significant economic losses
100 due to cankers caused by Botryosphaeriaceae species (Chen et al. 2013b). In many cases, when
101 the plant is infected in the nursery the cankers develop during the first years after plantation.
102 Phylogenetic studies have revealed 11 Botryosphaeriaceae species (*B. dothidea*, *D. olivarum*,
103 *Dothiorella iberica*, *Neofusicoccum australe*, *Neof. parvum*, *Neof. mediterraneum*, *Neof.*
104 *nonquaesitum*, *Lasiodiplodia theobromae*, *Diplodia seriata*, *Dot. sarmentorum*, and
105 *Macrophomina phaseolina*) associated with band and canopy cankers in California and Spain
106 (Chen et al. 2013b; Doll et al. 2015; Gramaje et al. 2012; Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Table 1).

107 Lower limb dieback (LLDB) is a complex syndrome known by farmers and farm advisors for
108 the past 20 years. To date, this syndrome has been described in California, but similar
109 symptoms to a lesser degree have been observed in Australian almond orchards (Michailides
110 et al. 2009; 2018). The affected almonds initially show yellow leaves in the lower canopy,
111 dieback of thin branches, and subsequently tufts of brown, blighted leaves. Although excess
112 moisture in the soil during spring seems to play a major role in this problem (Lampinen et al.
113 2009), *Botryosphaeria* and *Phomopsis* (anamorph of *Diaporthe*) species have sometimes been
114 isolated from symptomatic and asymptomatic branches of almond trees. In recent inoculation

115 experiments, neither *Botryosphaeria* nor *Phomopsis* species caused symptoms on branches that
116 resembled the LLDB symptoms. This fact, along with the absence of any effect of fungicide
117 applications, suggest that both species may be secondary colonizers of almond limbs
118 (Michailides et al. 2009).

119 *Olive*

120 Dalmatian disease of olive was first described in 1883 affecting fruit in the Dalmatia region of
121 Croatia (Thümen 1883). In the Mediterranean Basin, the disease is known as “escudete”
122 (translated as “small shield”) in Spanish and Portuguese (Moral et al. 2010). Escudete develops
123 in green fruit during the summer in sites associated with stings caused by the olive fly,
124 *Bactrocera oleae*, which is the most important pest of this crop (Iannotta et al. 2007; Moral et
125 al. 2010). The characteristic symptom is a sunken, necrotic, circular lesion with a well-defined
126 margin (Moral et al. 2010; Fig. 4A). During the winter, when the fruit is ripe, infected fruit will
127 drop to the ground and become mummified; yet the initial symptom (shield) remains visible
128 (Latinović et al. 2013; Moral et al. 2010; Fig. 4B). Escudete is widespread around the
129 Mediterranean Basin including France, Italy, Montenegro, Portugal, Spain, and Tunisia
130 (Chattaoui et al. 2011; Iannotta et al. 2007; Latinović et al. 2013; Margier 2014; Moral et al.
131 2010; Phillips et al. 2005; Zachos and Tzavella-Klonari 1979). The incidence of table fruit
132 showing the typical necrotic shield frequently exceeds the tolerance level for the 'Extra' Class
133 fruit, which is usually 2% or 4% (Moral et al. 2017a). The causal agent, which was originally
134 identified as *Phyllosticta dalmatica*, underwent several taxonomic changes during the first half
135 of the 20th century. In 1979, Zachos and Tzavella-Klonari (1979) classified the Dalmatian
136 isolates within the genus *Camarosporium* as *C. dalmaticum*. However, Phillips et al. (2005)
137 reclassified the pathogen as *B. dothidea* through DNA sequencing. Additionally, because ripe
138 fruit have reduced resistance to fungal rot, a plethora of fungi, including several
139 Botryosphaeriaceae species, can cause rot of black fruit (Moral et al., 2008). In this case, the
140 symptoms usually appear as brown or black decay that covers part or all the fruit, with pycnidia
141 formed on the fruit surface (Lazizzera et al. 2008a; 2008b; Sergeeva et al. 2009; Table 1).

142 In 2005, Romero and co-workers (2005) described branch dieback caused by
143 Botryosphaeriaceae species on olive cv. Gordal Sevillana in southern Spain. The pathogen
144 usually affects thin shoots (< 20 mm in diameter) that can show sunken cankers or open wounds
145 (Moral et al. 2010; 2017a). Overall, blighted shoots appear to be homogeneously distributed in
146 the olive canopy (Fig. 4C). The extent of yield losses caused by this disease are uncertain. The

147 pathogen kills productive shoots (and thereby cuts yield), but even if the infection does not
 148 cause the death of the affected branch, it reduces the normal growth of trees (Moral et al. 2010;
 149 2017a). In severely affected orchards, between 70 and 90% of mature olives cv. Gordal
 150 Sevillana show branch dieback, even under good management practices. In these orchards, the
 151 pathogen destroys up to 14% of the total canopy of the orchard, with individual trees showing
 152 >25% canopy volume loss. The pathogen was originally identified as *B. ribis* but was
 153 subsequently reclassified as *Neof. mediterraneum* (Moral et al. 2010). Nine
 154 Botryosphaeriaceae species have now been identified as causal agents of olive branch dieback
 155 in California, Italy, and Tunisia (Carlucci et al. 2013; Chattaoui et al. 2012; Kaliterna et al.
 156 2013; Moral et al. 2010; 2017a; Úrbez-Torres et al. 2013; Table 1).

157 ***Pistachio***

158 Panicle (i.e., a branched inflorescence) and shoot blight is the most important pistachio disease.
 159 The pathogen was reported as a new species of *Camarosporium* (*C. pistaciae*) in Greece in
 160 1974 (Zachos et al. 1974), and 10 years later as *B. dothidea* in California (Rice et al. 1985).
 161 The pathogen causes cankers that can reach up to 30 cm in length, covered with dark exudate
 162 when it occurs in the trunk or scaffold branches (Michailides and Morgan 2004). The fungus
 163 can invade the xylem and sometimes cause V-shaped cankers in cross section. The disease does
 164 not usually kill branches or entire trees; instead, pistachios can heal around cankers to prevent
 165 further expansion. Botryosphaeria panicle and shoot blight also causes major damage to current
 166 growth, including shoots, panicles, and leaves (Ntahimpera et al. 2002; Fig. 5A). Shoot
 167 infection can also occur at postharvest through bud, leaf, and panicle scars (Ahimera et al.
 168 2003; Michailides and Morgan 1992; Moral et al. 2017b). Shoots originating from heavily
 169 infected or partially killed buds expand briefly, then turn black and frequently collapse. The
 170 killing of male buds may not impact yield because male pistachio trees produce abundant
 171 pollen (Michailides and Morgan 2004). However, infection of flower buds of female trees can
 172 lead to infection of panicles at the rachis base; panicle collapse is the most devastating phase
 173 of the disease (Moral et al. 2017b). Furthermore, the pathogen can infect the base of the petiole
 174 or the base of the leaflet of pistachio leaf, leading to leaf or leaflet blight and defoliation during
 175 the summer. Direct infection of leaves via stomata leads to necrotic black lesions in the spring,
 176 whereas in the summer lesions have brown centers with chlorotic margins and develop some
 177 pycnidia scattered on the central surface of the lesion. Leaf infections become irregular to round
 178 brown lesions (≤ 25 mm in diameter) with chlorotic margins (Michailides and Morgan 2004).
 179 In pistachio fruit, direct infection via lenticels by Botryosphaeriaceae pathogens appear as

180 rounded, black, pin-head-sized (1 to 3 mm in diameter) lesions, but these lesions can cover
181 extensive areas and even the entire fruit (Fig. 5B). The epicarp may be covered with a layer of
182 pycnidia with an appearance like black pepper granules on the epicarp surface (Michailides
183 and Morgan 2004).

Page | 7

184 The pathogen causes extensive losses in pistachio-growing areas during epidemic years.
185 During the late 1980s, yield losses from 40 to 100% were common in the northern counties of
186 California (Michailides 1991; Michailides and Morgan 2004). In 1998, after a warm and
187 extraordinarily wet “El Niño” event, disease impact was very severe due to a combination of
188 favorable weather and ineffective fungicides. In the words of the Californian growers, it was a
189 “Bot year;” total production lost to the disease was estimated at 9 million kg (Michailides and
190 Morgan 2004). Pistachio production history in California shows several consecutive years of
191 severe epidemics due to panicle and shoot blight; for example, such a series began after a very
192 wet spring in 1995 and broke the upward linear trend of production during the “On years” (Fig.
193 6). In nurseries, Botryosphaeriaceae species also cause significant economic losses since the
194 pathogens cause stem cankers near the graft union that can result in the death of young trees
195 (Chen et al. 2014b; Swart and Botes 1995). Pistachio panicle and shoot blight has been
196 described in most countries growing pistachios, including Australia, Italy, Iran, Spain, and
197 South Africa (Armengol et al. 2008; Mohammadi et al. 2015; Slippers et al. 2007; Wunderlich
198 et al. 2012). The number of Botryosphaeriaceae species recorded in pistachio has increased to
199 15, including *B. dothidea*, *D. seriata*, *Dot. iberica*, *Dot. sarmentorum*, *Dot. viticola*, *L.*
200 *americana*, *L. citricola*, *L. gilanensis*, *L. theobromae*, *M. phaseolina*, *Neof. australe*, *Neof.*
201 *mediterraneum*, *Neof. hellenicum*, *Neof. parvum*, and *Neof. vitifusiforme* (Armengol et al.
202 2008; Chen et al. 2014a; 2014b; 2015; Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Table 1).

203 **Walnut**

204 Botryosphaeria canker and blight of walnut was described by H. Fawcett as “melaxuma of the
205 walnut” in 1915 in California, but farmers had noticed the disease since 1909 (Fawcett 1915).
206 The main symptoms are cankers on the trunk of young trees and scaffold branches of mature
207 trees (Fig. 5C). Dieback of spurs (short shoots that bear flower buds, and then flowers and fruit
208 in the following year) results from infections moving from affected fruit via the peduncle or
209 shoots through leaf and peduncle scars. Shoots and spurs infected by Botryosphaeriaceae fungi
210 show bumpy areas that are not uniformly distributed. In contrast, shoots infected by *Phomopsis*
211 species (also associated with the disease) produce pycnidia whose ostioles are uniformly

212 distributed on the surface of the shoot. Moreover, for Botryosphaeriaceae species that have
213 hyaline conidia the contents of pycnidia appear glassy and transparent, whereas pycnidia of
214 *Phomopsis* spp. appear cloudy and off-white following superficial, longitudinal sectioning of
215 the shoots. The husks of walnut fruit are highly susceptible to Botryosphaeriaceae infections;
216 the pathogens cause latent infections in developing fruit and black-brownish lesions in mature
217 ones. The lesions advance quickly, consuming the entire fruit and developing pycnidia (Fig.
218 5D). Lesions are usually restricted to the husk, but some species can colonize the kernel. Thus,
219 Botryosphaeriaceae spp. and *Phomopsis* spp. can be detected in infested (or killed) walnut buds
220 during winter (Michailides et al. 2014). Although economic losses are considerable, these are
221 difficult to estimate - first, because it is tough to separate damage caused by Botryosphaeriaceae
222 spp. from that caused by *Phomopsis* spp. (Michailides et al. 2014), and second, because
223 Botryosphaeriaceae spp. are frequently associated with walnuts showing decline due to natural
224 causes in well-maintained orchards or to pest injury, and whose etiology is difficult to
225 determine. Also, significant economic losses occur in nurseries due to infection of the graft
226 union, which is particularly susceptible to fungal infection in young walnuts (Chen et al.
227 2013a). Botryosphaeria canker and blight of walnut has been reported in many different
228 walnut-growing countries including China, Greece, Egypt, Iran, and Spain (Abdollahzadeh et
229 al. 2013; Haggag et al. 2007; Moral et al. 2010; Rumbos 1987; Yu et al. 2015) as well as the
230 U.S. Chen and co-workers (2014b) described the following ten species - *B. dothidea*, *D. mutila*,
231 *D. seriata*, *Dot. iberica*, *L. citricola*, *Neof. mediterraneum*, *Neof. nonquaesitum*, *Neof. parvum*,
232 *Neof. vitifusiforme*, and *N. dimidiatum* - affecting walnut in California (Table 1).

233 **Rise of the diseases**

234 In the last decade or so, we have observed a rise in the number and severity of diseases caused
235 by Botryosphaeriaceae fungi that can be attributed to several causes.

236 ***Agricultural practices***

237 In California and the Mediterranean Basin, nut crops and olive plantings are often established
238 in humid areas such as near riverbanks that provide a favorable environment for infection and
239 where wild hosts (blackberry, black walnut, cottonwood, deodar cedar, eucalyptus, willow, and
240 others) of Botryosphaeriaceae spp. frequently thrive (Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Michailides et al.
241 2014; Moral et al. 2010; Figs. 7A-B). In the San Joaquin Valley of California, for example,
242 almonds, grapes, pistachios, walnuts, and olives grow in contiguous areas, allowing a flow of
243 inoculum among these hosts. Similarly, olive and other woody crops affected by

244 Botryosphaeriaceae spp. (e.g., almond and grapevine) usually grow in neighboring orchards
245 in Mediterranean countries (Figs. 7C-D). Furthermore, rising land prices, shifting agronomic
246 trends, and increasing profitability of almond, pistachio, olive, and walnut production have
247 resulted in the redesign of orchards during the last 40 years. For example, plant density has
248 increased to modern super-high-density systems called hedgerow systems. In the hedgerow
249 systems (Fig. 1F), the trees are closely planted in the row forming a continuous canopy where
250 the productive unit is the linear meter of the row rather than the individual tree (Díez et al.
251 2016). Currently, hedgerow systems are common for walnut and olive production, and the first
252 trials with almonds are being conducted. For many pathosystems, microclimatic changes
253 resulting from higher plant densities can create conditions more conducive to disease
254 development by increasing the duration of wetness on the tree canopy. For example,
255 anthracnose epidemics, caused by *Colletotrichum* species, progress faster in hedgerow olive
256 plantings than in high-density ones (Moral et al. 2012).

257 In California and Spain, olives in hedgerow systems are harvested using canopy-contact
258 harvesters (grape harvesters), whereas almonds, pistachios, olive (in traditional plantations),
259 and walnuts are usually harvested using mechanical trunk shakers that vibrate the trunk for a
260 few seconds, resulting in fruit drop. Both trunk shakers and canopy-contact harvesters cause
261 several types of injuries to the trees such as loss of portions of trunk bark or wounding and
262 breaking of scaffold branches that facilitate infection by Botryosphaeriaceae species. Likewise,
263 wounds caused by pruning tools facilitate infection by these and other fungal species such as
264 Basidiomycetes (Michailides 1991; Úrbez-Torres et al. 2013; Figs. 8A-E). Both hand pruning
265 and mechanical pruning methods are used on nut crops and olive trees with varying frequency
266 and intensity, depending on the area where the crop is growing and the intensity of crop
267 production. For instance, most of California almond and Turkish pistachio orchards hold as
268 their general principle, “*the more you prune, the more you reduce yield,*” whereas, in much of
269 the Mediterranean Basin, traditional pistachio and olive orchards implement annual hand
270 pruning. In any case, if conditions are conducive and inoculum is present, pruning wounds may
271 become infected, and cankers may develop around the wounds (Agustí-Brisach et al. 2019;
272 Michailides and Morgan 2004). Both harvesters and pruning tools can also move inoculum of
273 pathogens within and between orchards. In summary, more intensive cropping systems are
274 susceptible to a higher risk of infection by Botryosphaeriaceae species as a result of extended
275 periods of wetness, decreased the sunlight penetration into tree canopies, more wounding of

276 trees, and ultimately more inoculum sources (i.e., symptomatic trees) per orchard area, thereby
277 increasing the opportunity for infection.

278 We have also observed exacerbation of almond band canker associated with the use of vigorous
279 rootstocks (e.g., cv. Hansen) since these rootstocks cause more growth cracks in the trunks (i.e.
280 entryways of infection) than the less vigorous rootstocks (Moral et al., 2019). Finally, increased
281 regulatory restriction on the use of effective fungicides may have amplified damage caused by
282 these pathogens. For example, following the removal of benomyl (particularly effective against
283 *Botryosphaeria* species) for use in the European Community, major outbreaks of *Neof.*
284 *mediterraneum* affecting olives in southern Spain were reported (Moral et al. 2010; Romero et
285 al. 2005). Over the years, outbreaks of some fungal diseases have been associated with
286 resistance to certain fungicides, but this has not been clearly demonstrated for diseases caused
287 by Botryosphaeriaceae species (Michailides and Morgan 2004).

288 ***Buildup of inoculum***

289 Extreme weather conditions (El Niño and drought years) could have affected other fungi such
290 as *Phomopsis* species or pests such as walnut scale (*Quadraspidiotus juglansregiae*) and
291 stinkbugs (Hemiptera) attacking pistachio and almond, thus increasing the pressure of parasitic
292 organisms in the tree and increasing vulnerability to outbreaks of Botryosphaeriaceae-incited
293 diseases (Michailides et al. 2013; 2014; Michailides and Morgan 2016). For example, the
294 susceptibility of walnut branches to different Botryosphaeriaceae species increased when
295 scales were present in them (Moral et al. 2019). Large hemipteran insects (*Leptoglossus*
296 *clypealis*, *Chlorocoa*, and *Thyantha* spp.) facilitate pathogen infection by not only spreading
297 Botryosphaeriaceae pathogens but also creating wounds in host tissue (Michailides et al. 2014).
298 In olives, the traditional burning of pruning residues reduces fungal inoculum. Currently,
299 however, prunings are chipped and mulched onto the ground, which may increase inoculum in
300 orchards. In walnut, however, composting debris generated in hullers, even when 90% of the
301 hulls had pycnidia of Botryosphaeriaceae or Diaporthaceae fungi, resulted in no survival of
302 these pathogens; it is therefore considered safe to return composted material back in the orchard
303 (Michailides et al. 2014; Moral et al. 2019).

304 ***Weather conditions and climate change***

305 Risk of an outbreak of Botryosphaeriaceae-incited diseases peaks in seasons with excessive
306 rainfall due to infection occurring mainly from water-splashed conidia (Ahimera et al. 2004).
307 Because pathogen infections during the fall and winter frequently remain latent until the next

308 spring and summer, accumulation of latent infections and buildup of inoculum during periods
309 with high rainfall also increases the risk of disease in subsequent years (Michailides and
310 Morgan 2004). The occurrence of “El Niño” events at irregular intervals of two to seven years
311 can lead to cyclic epidemics where these diseases are not managed every year. Also, if a year
312 with high rainfall is followed by a drought year, symptoms caused by Botryosphaeriaceae
313 species are typically severe because of periods of water stress increase host susceptibility
314 (Marsberg et al. 2017; Piškur et al. 2011; Stanosz et al. 2001; Sturrock et al. 2011). For
315 example, pistachios under water stress show greater susceptibility to *Neof. mediterraneum* than
316 non-stressed trees (Ma et al. 2001). Trees severely damaged by low temperatures can also
317 become more susceptible to pathogens due to increased cracking and wounding. In Croatia,
318 Kaliterna and co-workers (2013) described an epidemic of *D. seriata* (usually a weak pathogen)
319 associated with dieback of young olive trees that had been exposed to exceptionally
320 low temperatures during the previous winter.

321 More frequent extreme weather is predicted by most climate change models, along with a
322 significant increase of summer air temperature and water stress on many crops in the
323 Mediterranean Basin (Lung et al. 2013). In California, in addition to an increase of temperature,
324 recent predictions point to an increase in annual precipitation from 3.3 to 15.2% (Allen and
325 Luptowitz 2017). Both increased plant stress (Mediterranean Basin) and precipitation
326 (California) could increase the severity of Botryosphaeriaceae-incited diseases.

327 **One pathogen on multiple hosts and one host with multiple pathogens**

328 To date, no Botryosphaeriaceae species has been identified that is specific to particular nut or
329 olive crops. Instead, almost all plant-pathogenic species in this family occur on multiple species
330 within these crop groups. However, *Dot. viticola* has been described only from pistachio among
331 the crops in this review (Mohammadi et al. 2015), and *D. pinea* and *D. scrobiculata* cause olive
332 fruit rot but have not been reported from almond, pistachio, or walnut (Lazzizera et al. 2008b).
333 In contrast, *B. dothidea*, *D. seriata*, *Neof. mediterraneum*, and *Neof. parvum* can infect
334 almonds, olives, pistachios, and walnuts (Chen et al. 2014a; 2014b; Gramaje et al. 2012;
335 Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Lazzizera et al. 2008a; 2008b; 2010; Úrbez-Torres et al. 2013). *Diplodia*
336 and *Dothiorella* species are weakly virulent in almond, pistachio, olive, and walnut crops,
337 whereas *L. citricola*, *Neof. mediterraneum*, and *Neof. nonquaesitum* are considered at least
338 moderately virulent (Chent et al. 2014; Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Moral et al. 2010; Úrbez-Torres
339 et al. 2013). Interestingly, *B. dothidea* is not considered to be a highly virulent pathogen in any

340 of these crops (Table 1). Differences in virulence have also been observed among isolates
341 belonging to the same species (Moral et al. 2017a).

342 In California and Spain, virulence of a given Botryosphaeriaceae species in a given host
343 may not necessarily be correlated with its isolation frequency. The pathogen's fitness can also
344 depend on other factors such as i) its virulence in nearby cultivated and wild hosts' ii) biology
345 of its saprophytic phase, iii) adaptation to prevailing climate conditions, and iv) resistance to
346 fungicides. For example, *D. seriata*, which is considered a weakly virulent pathogen in olive
347 and nut crops (Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Moral et al. 2010; Table 2), was the most frequently
348 isolated species from almond orchards showing tree decline in Mallorca, Spain (Olmo et al.
349 2016). In contrast, *D. seriata* is considered a minor species in California orchards, where the
350 moderate virulent species *Neof. mediterraneum* is dominant in pistachio (86% of isolations),
351 walnut (76% of isolations), almond, and olive orchards (Chen et al. 2014a; 2014b; Inderbitzin
352 et al. 2010; Moral et al. 2010). In the Andalusia region of Spain, after monitoring the fungal
353 fruiting structures on blighted branches from several commercial olive orchards, it was
354 determined that 26.3% of them were *Neof. mediterraneum*. (Moral et al. 2015; 2017a).

355 DISEASE CYCLE

356 The disease cycles of Botryosphaeriaceae species in almond, pistachio, olive, and walnut crops
357 are influenced by the perennial nature of these crops and by the climate. In general,
358 Mediterranean climates are typified by at least two consecutive dry months during the summer
359 and a cool or mild, wet winter. Asexual spores (pycnidiospores) are the main inoculum source,
360 and sexual spores (ascospores) have a limited role in the disease cycle (Inderbitzin et al. 2010;
361 Michailides and Morgan, 2004; Moral et al. 2010; 2015b; Fig. 9). Depending on the disease,
362 epidemic risk can be strongly influenced by the presence of insects that may increase the plant's
363 susceptibility or act as vectors (Table 2). Botryosphaeriaceae species have a saprophytic phase
364 in which they colonize tree bark as well as plant tissues that have fallen to the soil surface
365 (Michailides et al. 2018).

366 In contrast to the general disease cycle shown in Figure 9, *M. phaseolina* is primarily a root
367 pathogen. It is well-known as the causal agent of a decline of olive (Sánchez-Hernández et al.
368 1998; Sergeeva et al. 2005) and young almonds in commercial orchards (Michailides unpubl.).
369 Recently, we documented several hundred young olive trees (cv. Sikitita) affected by *M.*
370 *phaseolina* in southern Spain, attributed to a high density of inoculum due to previous
371 plantation of sunflower, and increased susceptibility due to irrigation with semisaline water

372 (Moral unpubl.).

373 **Pathogen survival**

374 ***On crops***

375 Botryosphaeriaceae species can overwinter and oversummer as pycnidia or pseudothecia, which develop within a stroma. Often, the stroma develops a wall that is only a few cells thick covering the fruiting bodies (Brooks and Ferrin 1993), whereas in other cases it exhibits a thick, strongly melanized tissue (Moral et al. 2007). In general, thicker stromata are more resistant to degradation. Epidermal layers of infected tissues can also protect the stroma and fruiting bodies from climatic factors and fungicides. Botryosphaeriaceae species can survive in cankered trunks, killed branches, blighted shoots and spurs, killed buds, and blighted fruit (English 1975; Michailides 1991). If the pathogen infects plant tissues that develop yearly (for example, fruit or leaves of deciduous trees), the pathogen survives the intervening period in infected tissues (cankered or not) on the tree canopy or the ground (Moral et al. 2010; 2017b). In the latter case, saprophytic microorganisms compete with the pathogen, decreasing its viability. Survival of the pathogen is markedly reduced if cankered branches are chipped. Michailides (1991) reported that infected rachises and fruit are retained on pistachios longer than healthy ones. In this host, viable pycnidiospores are recoverable from blighted rachis and cankers for 2 to 6 years, respectively (Michailides 1991). The presence of pycnidia or pseudothecia in the branches heavily depends on the host, thus, while fruiting bodies are easily found in cankered branches of pistachios, olives, and walnuts (Michailides and Morgan 2004; Moral et al. 2015; 2017a; Úrbez-Torres et al. 2013), they are rarely found in almond shoots or spurs. However, pseudothecia intermixed with abundant pycnidia have been found in the bark of almond trunks with severe band canker symptoms, in stumps of almonds killed by Botryosphaeriaceae species (Michailides et al. 2009), and in blighted shoots of walnuts found on the ground under the trees and attached on the tree. In the case of pistachio and walnut, Botryosphaeriaceae species can also overwinter in infected and blighted buds (Ntahimpera et al. 2002; Michailides and Morgan 2004; Michailides et al. 2014).

399 ***Alternative hosts and the environment***

400 When healthy trees from a nursery are planted, spores arrive from neighboring trees within the same field or nearby alternative hosts, whereas within affected orchards internal sources of inoculum cause most new infections (Figs. 10 and 11). Except for *M. phaseolina*, which survives in soil for long periods as microsclerotia, most Botryosphaeriaceae species appear to

404 survive poorly in the soil.

405 **Sources of inoculum and spore dispersal**

406 Botryosphaeriaceae species can develop inoculum in all tree tissues. In Californian pistachios,
407 pycnidia forming on blighted tissues are the main source of inoculum for panicle and shoot
408 blight (Chen et al. 2014a; Michailides 1991; Michailides and Morgan 2004). However,
409 pseudothecia are common in chaparral vegetation and other woody hosts in California
410 (Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Michailides and Morgan 2004; Moral et al. 2010). In almonds with
411 LLDB, pycnidia of Botryosphaeriaceae species did not develop in the affected limbs, which
412 instead bore pycnidia of *Phomopsis* species (Michailides et al. 2009). Hence, it is questionable
413 whether the dead shoots of almond can serve as sources of inoculum for Botryosphaeriaceae
414 species. Instead, pycnidia of the pathogen intermingled with pseudothecia are frequent in the
415 bark of cankered almonds trunks and scaffold branches. Stumps of removed trees and other
416 hosts in the proximity of almond orchard can also serve as sources of inoculum (English 1975).
417 Inoculum sources of Botryosphaeriaceae diseases affecting walnuts and olives are less known,
418 although in both hosts the cankered shoots, branches, spurs, and fruit (in the case of the walnut)
419 frequently appear covered by fruiting bodies (Moral et al. 2010; 2015b; Michailides et al.
420 2015). In both olive and walnut trees, viable pycnidiospores and ascospores can also be found
421 in attached or fallen cankered branches.

422 ***Water-dispersed pycnidiospores***

423 Under humid conditions, pycnidia of Botryosphaeriaceae species exude a hyaline (or dark) and
424 viscous matrix, called a cirrhus, whose pycnidiospores are spread mainly by splashing rain but
425 also by sprinkler irrigation, insects, animals, and tools (Ahimera et al. 2004; Michailides 1991;
426 Michailides and Morgan, 1993; Michailides and Morgan, 2016). The spread of pycnidiospores
427 can occur at any time during the growing season, causing primary or secondary infections.
428 Under natural conditions, rainfall of at least 16 mm is needed for releasing pycnidiospores in
429 cirrhi of *Neof. mediterraneum* (Morgan et al. 2009). The rainwater splashing or dripping from
430 severely affected pistachios can contain up to 6×10^4 pycnidiospores per ml (Ahimera et al.
431 2004).

432 The number of pycnidiospores disseminated during rain events has been represented by one-
433 or two-phase exponential decay curves since most spores are released soon after the onset of
434 rain. Cirrhi are not exuded during dry periods because they require hydration to develop. For
435 example, most pycnidiospores of *Neof. mediterraneum* are released within the first hour after

436 the onset of rain or irrigation (Michailides and Morgan 1993). “Power law” or a “negative
437 exponential law” models (Campbell and Madden 1990) were used by Ahimera and co-workers
438 (2004) to describe the dispersion gradient of *Neof. mediterraneum* from pistachio branches.

439 *Aerially dispersed ascospores*

Page | 15

440 Sexual reproduction has been little studied in the Botryosphaeriaceae. The type of sexual
441 reproduction is not clear but may include homothallism (self-compatibility) in some species
442 (Marsberg et al. 2017; Slippers and Wingfield 2007) and heterothallism (self-sterile, i.e.,
443 compatible strains in different isolates) in others (Bihon et al. 2014). In California,
444 pseudothecial stages of *B. dothidea* and *Neof. parvum* have been detected on symptomatic
445 almond and olive branches (Chen et al. 2014a; Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Moral et al. 2010). In
446 Andalusia, Spain, 1.1% of *Neof. mediterraneum* fruiting bodies developing in cankered olive
447 branches were pseudothecia (Moral et al. 2015). Because pseudothecia develop from
448 November to December on affected olive branches, it explains the early (during February)
449 appearance of the first disease symptoms in orchards of this region (Moral et al. 2015). In
450 California, 1.8% of the fruiting bodies that developed in walnut branches cankered by
451 Botryosphaeriaceae species were pseudothecia of unknown species (most likely of *B. dothidea*;
452 Michailides et al. 2014).

453 Production of ascospores has several epidemiological implications. A higher level of genotypic
454 diversity is expected in pathogen populations with sexual recombination than exclusively
455 asexual populations (McDonald and Linde 2002), as well as a greater dissemination capacity
456 than conidia since ascospores can be carried by both splashing and air currents. As for
457 pycnidiospores, however, weather parameters such as intensity, amount, duration of rainfall
458 and velocity and turbulence of wind can affect the dispersal capacity of ascospores (Mahaffee
459 and Stoll 2016).

460 *Vectoring by insects*

461 Olive escudete is the most notorious disease that includes interaction between
462 Botryosphaeriaceae species and insects. In 2013, Eldesouki-Arafat showed that *B. dothidea* is
463 spread by the midge *Prolasioptera berlesiana* (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae: Lasiopterini). The
464 female of this cecidomyiid species has a special structure called a mycangium in the abdomen
465 that is adapted to transport *B. dothidea* spores (Eldesouki-Arafat 2013; Moral et al. 2016).
466 Mycangia are characteristic of mutualistic interactions between midges and fungi (Bissett and
467 Borkent 1988; Heath and Stireman 2010). The midge is attracted by ovipositor punctures on

468 the fruit surface made by the olive fly (*Bactrocera oleae*) and deposits its own eggs adjacent
469 to the fly's eggs, thereby also inoculating the fungus into the puncture. The cecidomyiid larvae
470 feed on *B. dothidea* mycelium in false punctures (no oviposition, so no fly egg present) made
471 by the fly, ostensibly to avoid predation by the cecidomyiid larvae (Eldesouki-Arafat 2013;
472 Moral et al. 2016). The first symptoms of escudete are frequently observed in the first half of
473 August, during the period of fly punctures (Eldesouki-Arafat 2013). This mutualistic
474 interaction of *B. dothidea* with *P. berlesiana* explains why this weakly virulent fungal species
475 is the sole causal agent of the disease (Moral et al. 2016). Although the olive fly appeared in
476 California in 1998 (Rice et al. 2006) and *B. dothidea* and the susceptible cultivars are also
477 present, the absence of *P. berlesiana* explains the absence of escudete in the state.

478 Pistachios in California are sometimes severely damaged by hemipteran species, such as
479 *Leptoglossus clypealis* and *Thyanta pallidovirens*, which puncture the nuts, causing abortion
480 of fruitlets, epicarp lesion, or kernel necrosis (Michailides and Morgan 2016). Of these
481 hemipteran species, around 30% of *Thyanta* stinkbugs carry propagules of *Neof.*
482 *mediterraneum* externally on their body, while this percentage ranges from 1 to 11.8% in the
483 case of *Lep. clypealis*. In this latter species, the pathogen can also be isolated from excrement
484 samples, which points to the possibility of an internal spread of the pathogen in the digestive
485 system of the insect (Michailides and Morgan 2016).

486 ***Machinery and tools***

487 Botryosphaeriaceae species can be spread via contaminated pruning tools (e.g., shears and
488 saws) and other equipment. In California, we have frequently isolated species of this family
489 from pruning wounds in pistachio and walnut orchards severely affected by cankers and branch
490 dieback. Likewise, the clamps of trunk shakers are also a potential source of infection for
491 almonds that often suffer cankers in the trunk. When hedging of walnuts or pistachios is done,
492 the pruning saws can cut through branches covered with pycnidia and inoculate the wounds in
493 healthy ones (Michailides et al. 2015). The canopy-contact harvesters, used in the hedgerow
494 orchards, are a potential spreading vehicle within and among orchards. The dispersion of
495 Botryosphaeriaceae inoculum by tools and equipment could explain the aggregated pattern of
496 affected almond or olive trees growing into the same row that is often observed (Moral and
497 Michailides unpubl.).

498 ***Infected nursery plants***

499 Botryosphaeriaceae species can cause symptomless (latent) infections in young plants that are

500 readily dispersed in nursery shipments. The species *D. seriata*, *L. citricola*, *L. theobromae*, and
501 *N. dimidiatum* impact pistachio and walnut plants in nurseries (Chen et al. 2013a; 2013b; Swart
502 and Botes 1995). For potted plants, the presence of soil increases the risk of dispersion of soil-
503 borne pathogens such as *M. phaseolina*.

Page | 17

504 **Pre-infection, infection, and colonization**

505 Once pycnidiospores or ascospores land on susceptible tissues of a host, they trigger several
506 pre-infection processes such as adhesion, spore germination, and host recognition (Sammonds
507 et al. 2016). Temperature, water potential, and the presence of antagonistic microorganisms
508 can delay or inhibit spore germination (Chen et al. 2003). During this process, the hyaline and
509 aseptate *Fusicoccum*-like pycnidiospores may develop one or two septa and become pale
510 brown. In some cases, Botryosphaeriaceae spp. can develop an appressorium that facilitates
511 mechanical penetration of host tissue (Kim et al. 1999). The pathogens frequently produce
512 enzymes, which help to break down the cuticle and cell walls, and toxins (botryosphaerans,
513 isosclerone, and tyrosol) that aid colonization (Andolfi et al. 2011; Esteves et al. 2014).
514 Botryosphaeriaceae species can also cause infection directly through natural openings such as
515 stomata and lenticels (Brown and Britton 1986; Kim et al. 1999; Michailides 1991).

516 The presence of wounds facilitates infection, and severe symptoms are often associated with
517 different types of wounds on lignified and green tissues (Michailides 1991; Michailides and
518 Morgan 2004; Moral et al. 2017b). In almond band canker, plant infection occurs through
519 growth cracks that serve as entryways of infection (Fig. 3A). Almond infection can also occur
520 through wounds on fruit and peduncles as well as cracks at the base of shoots and scaffold
521 branches due to wind damage and pruning wounds. Aggressive cankers are often initiated from
522 major pruning cuts and can ultimately kill trees. Wounding caused by Hemipteran insects
523 exacerbates fruit infection, resulting in a high severity of disease in California pistachios
524 (Michailides and Morgan 2016). Sap that oozes onto the epicarp after fruit puncturing favors
525 spore germination and growth of *Neof. mediterraneum* by providing the needed moisture and
526 nutrients. However, once the sap dries it can protect the wound against subsequent infections
527 (Moral et al. 2017b).

528 In walnut, pathogen infection occurs either directly in wounded or nonwounded hulls or
529 through wounds and scars caused by fruit and leaf peduncles (Michailides et al. 2013). The
530 infection and colonization of shoots and spurs of walnut are distinctive because colonization
531 frequently begins in the husk of one fruit, spreads to adjacent fruits, colonizes the peduncle,

532 and, then moves into the spur and shoot, causing canker and blight (Michailides et al. 2014;
533 Fig. 5D). Walnut branches are characterized by the presence of brownish segmented pith,
534 which facilitates and advances the longitudinal colonization of the branches by the pathogen.
535 Pith infection can occur up to 5 cm in advance of colonization of woody tissues. Infections
536 then move into the tissues surrounding the pith and subsequently extend into the xylem (Agusti-
537 Brisach et al. 2019).

538 **Saprophytic phase**

539 Botryosphaeriaceae species can colonize dead tissues such as the outer bark of trunks of nut
540 crops and other perennial woody crops; old cankers caused by *Botrytis cinerea* in pistachios;
541 or shoots and branches killed by *Verticillium dahliae* or *Phytophthora* spp. in almonds,
542 pistachios, and olive. In California orchards, Botryosphaeriaceae species and the bacterium
543 *Xanthomonas arboricola* pv. *juglandis* are often isolated together from necrotic lesions on
544 walnut fruit, suggesting that the bacterium can enter through the styler end and cause necrosis,
545 after which the fungus may follow (Michailides et al. 2014). The pathogen can colonize other
546 dead tissues (i.e., branches killed by branch wilt in walnut) and branches and shoots pruned
547 and left on the ground. This saprophytic ability could explain why Botryosphaeriaceae species
548 are readily isolated from healthy pistachio and almond branches in California.

549 **EPIDEMIOLOGY**

550 Botryosphaeriaceae species are monocyclic or oligocyclic pathogens that cause polyetic
551 epidemics. As monocyclic pathogens, they complete one disease cycle, or even part of one, in
552 one season. Depending on the weather conditions, these species can be oligocyclic pathogens,
553 i.e., polycyclic pathogens with a few (two or three) disease cycles per season. In both cases,
554 epidemic development and symptom severity are largely dependent on initial inoculum (Table
555 2). In polyetic epidemics, inoculum generated during one season contributes to primary
556 inoculum during the next season (Zadoks and Schein 1979). For this reason, the time course
557 of epidemics of diseases caused by Botryosphaeriaceae species may extend for several
558 successive years.

559 **Factors influencing disease development**

560 *Weather parameters*

561 Infections in olives, pistachios, and walnuts can occur at any time during the season if there is
562 splashing water and suitable temperatures (10-35°C) to induce spore germination (Ahimera et

563 al. 2003; Michailides and Morgan 1992; 1993; 2004; Moral et al. 2010). Pycnidiospore
564 germination and germ tube elongation require free water or relative humidity $\geq 90\%$ (Ma et al.
565 2001; Arauz and Sutton 1989). Temperatures of 25-30°C are considered optimal for spore
566 germination, but optima vary among species, isolates within species, and spore type (Copes
567 and Hendrix 2004; Michailides and Morgan 1992; Úrbez-Torres et al. 2010). For example,
568 both Spanish and Greek isolates of *B. dothidea* causing escudete showed an optimum of 30°C
569 for conidial germination, suggesting that the pathogen is well adapted to high summer
570 temperatures. However, germination of spores was almost nil at 35°C for Greek isolates and at
571 45°C for Spanish isolates (Zachos and Tzavella-Klonari 1979; Moral et al. 2010). Similarly,
572 pycnidiospores of *Neof. mediterraneum* isolates from pistachio that germinated at $>36^\circ\text{C}$
573 frequently failed to develop colonies (Michailides and Morgan 1992). Dry periods occurring
574 between wet periods can also affect spore germination (Arauz and Sutton 1990). For example,
575 alternating wet with dry periods during germination of spores of *Neofusicoccum* spp. resulted
576 in development of 2 to 3 septa in the spores and brown coloration (Michailides 1991).
577 Temperature and humidity also influence pycnidia, whose numbers increased linearly in
578 affected branches as temperature increased from 10 to 35°C (Michailides and Morgan 1992).
579 High temperatures are also associated with symptom expression. For example, in pistachio, the
580 first blighted symptoms usually appear with the increase of temperature at the end of spring or
581 beginning of summer, when panicle collapse can occur in a few weeks (Mila et al. 2005; Moral
582 et al. 2017b; Morgan and Michailides 1992). Light intensity and duration also affect pycnidia
583 development and pathogen sporulation, but these relationships are poorly understood.

584 ***Inoculum potential: inoculum density and pathogen virulence***

585 Botryosphaeriaceae species exhibit substantial differences in virulence (Table 1). Also, the
586 inoculum density of Botryosphaeriaceae species at a given time depends on the period of the
587 season (Ahimera et al. 2004; Moral et al. 2017b) and on the final disease severity during the
588 previous season. Fungicide residues and antagonist microorganisms over the plant surface also
589 affect the inoculum potential by altering the spores' viability. The distance to other hosts (i.e.,
590 donors of spore inoculum) can have a substantial impact on local inoculum density and thereby
591 the spatial pattern of disease incidence. For example, in almond orchards affected by band
592 canker, the severity of symptoms declined with distance from external inoculum sources (Fig.
593 10; Michailides et al. 2018). In sum, the spatial pattern of disease severity in a given plot is a
594 combined effect of internal inoculum, distance to the external inoculum sources, and edge
595 effect.

596 ***Plant susceptibility***

597 With almond band canker, the main period of infection seems to be during the spring when
598 moderate temperatures and rain are present, or sprinkler irrigation water wets the trunk of the
599 trees (Michailides et al. 2009). During this season, rapid radial growth of the almond trunk
600 frequently causes growth cracks. In inoculation tests, young almonds are susceptible to
601 infection by *B. dothidea* across the entire season, but cankers develop and grow fastest in the
602 early spring (Michailides et al. 2009; 2018). In the case of pistachio shoots, susceptibility
603 decreases across the season as lignification proceeds (Michailides 1991). In contrast,
604 susceptibility of pistachio buds to infection increases exponentially from mid-February
605 (dormant buds) to mid-March (swelling to expanding buds) (Michailides and Morgan 2004).
606 Susceptibility of pistachio nuts increases from May to late July, when the kernel has almost
607 reached its full size, then decreases until it reaches a level similar to that during spring (Mila
608 et al. 2005; Ntahimpera et al. 2002). Vigorous walnut shoots are resistant to pathogen infection
609 during the spring when there is a high accumulation of phenols. Similarly, walnut spurs show
610 high resistance to pathogen infection during May, then increasing susceptibility from June to
611 the end of August. In field experiments, inoculation of immature and maturing walnut nuts
612 later resulted in blighted fruit (Michailides et al. 2015). However, when the inoculations were
613 conducted in August and September, the incidence of fruit blight was higher (Michailides et
614 al. 2014). This temporal pattern suggests that autumn infections can result in more damage to
615 walnut nuts because these infections have a higher probability of causing fruit blight and decay
616 of kernels than infections initiated in the spring. In olive fruit, developing drupes are almost
617 immune to *Botryosphaeria* infection due to an ontogenic resistance to infection that correlates
618 with rising levels of phenolic compounds during fruit development (Moral et al. 2010; 2019).

619 The factors that trigger symptom development in plant tissues with latent infection of
620 Botryosphaeriaceae species are unknown, although nutritional (i.e., increase in carbohydrates),
621 weather (i.e., temperature increase), and host factors (i.e., drought stress), as well as changes
622 in the dynamics and densities of antifungal compounds (i.e., specific phenolic compounds) on
623 the green tissues and fruit, have been reported to induce symptom development (Ma et al. 2001;
624 Morgan and Michailides 1992; Ntahimpera et al. 2002).

625 ***Soil properties***

626 Excessively wet soil conditions during the spring, which can decrease the amount of oxygen
627 available for the roots, followed by a rapid decline of the soil water content may play a primary

628 role in defoliation and loss of viability of almond branches in the lower half (LLDB) of tree
629 canopies (Lampinen et al. 2009). Subsequently, *Botryosphaeria* and *Phomopsis* species can act
630 as secondary pathogens or saprophytes affecting branches weakened by soil water stress
631 (Michailides et al. 2009).

632 ***Insects***

633 The population of Hemipteran insects on pistachio panicles was directly correlated with
634 symptom severity caused by *Neof. mediterraneum* (Michailides and Morgan 2016). Likewise,
635 high severity of walnut *Botryosphaeria* canker and blight was associated with high density of
636 walnut scale (*Quadraspidiotus juglansregiae*), since severe damage by scale predisposes
637 walnut shoots to disease (Michailides et al. 2013; 2014). As one might expect considering the
638 disease cycle of olive “escudete”, higher *Bactrocera* fly populations (and after that, higher
639 incidence of oviposition punctures on fruit caused by female flies) resulted in more severe
640 outbreaks of *B. dothidea*-incited symptoms (Eldesouki-Arafat 2013; Moral et al. 2016).

641 **Disease forecasting**

642 Because the severity and economic impact of Botryosphaeriaceae diseases differ substantially
643 among seasons — years with epidemics often alternate with years during which symptoms are
644 few or absent — these diseases are suitable candidates for forecasting. Disease forecasting
645 enables farmers to use host, pathogen, and environmental conditions to help them determine
646 when to initiate disease management actions. In this way, disease forecasting can help to reduce
647 the use of pesticides by farmers.

648 ***Forecast based on primary infection***

649 Initial efforts to provide a forecast scheme for pistachio panicle and shoot blight were focused
650 on primary infection by the pathogen. These models were based on the knowledge that buds
651 can be infested/infected during the previous season, and that early infections of developing
652 fruit during spring remain latent until later in the growing season. According to the BUDMON
653 (BUD MONitoring) model, split or intact buds collected at the end of winter are plated on
654 culture media to quantify the percentage of affected buds, which is linearly correlated with the
655 final severity of symptoms (Michailides and Morgan 2004; Ntahimpera et al. 2002). In old
656 plantings, BUDMON provides a pre-season prediction of disease risk, whereas in young
657 plantings it determines when an orchard that was formerly free of *Botryosphaeria* starts
658 showing invasion by the pathogen, which triggers annual monitoring to avoid major losses
659 (Michailides and Morgan, 2004). After finding that walnut buds are too infested/infected by

660 Botryosphaeriaceae, we applied the BUDMON bioassay to determine whether predicted
661 Botryosphaeria canker and blight of walnut (Michailides et al. 2013; 2014). Although the
662 BUDMON bioassay is successful in predicting final disease severity, weather conditions after
663 bud sprouting, which are not taken into account by BUDMON, impact symptom severity
664 affecting the accuracy of this method (Mila et al. 2005; Morgan et al. 2009).

Page | 22

665 From mid-June to early July, the Overnight Freezing-Incubation Technique (ONFIT) provides
666 a useful forecast of end-of-season infection intensity of pistachio panicle and shoot blight. The
667 percentage of latent infections in developing pistachio nuts or leaves is detected by incubation
668 of previously frozen developing fruit in humid chambers (Michailides and Morgan 2004).
669 Because ONFIT provides quantification of latent infection during the spring and early summer,
670 and later rainfall events are very sporadic in Mediterranean conditions, this technique
671 frequently offers a better forecast of the final disease intensity than BUDMON. However,
672 ONFIT can underestimate final disease incidence in years with few latent infections but
673 unusually disease-favorable environmental conditions during summer (Morgan et al. 2009).

674 *Forecast based on weather parameters*

675 Pistachio panicle and shoot blight is impacted by rainfall during the spring, which favors latent
676 infections, and cumulative temperature during the summer, which can trigger symptom
677 development (Mila et al. 2005; Mila and Michailides 2006). We developed a simple degree-
678 day model for summer in which accumulation of 40 h of $\geq 32^{\circ}\text{C}$ was effective for decision-
679 making in years with relatively few rain events (Mila et al. 2005). The Botryosphaeria Infection
680 Model (BIM) which considered that pathogen infection occurs when the temperature is $\geq 11^{\circ}\text{C}$
681 and rainfall of ≥ 1 mm/h occurred for ≥ 4 h (Michailides and Morgan 2004), was superseded
682 by the Leaf Wetness Model (LWM), which also uses temperature as an independent variable,
683 and replaces rainfall variables by wetness duration (Morgan et al. 2009; Fig. 11). This LWM
684 is popular with California pistachio farmers since it enables effective control of the disease
685 with a reduced number of early-season sprays (Morgan et al. 2009; Fig. 12).

686 The BUDMON and LWM models can be combined to improve disease risk assessment
687 accuracy (Morgan et al. 2009). Also, the ONFIT method estimates the incidence of latent
688 infections and aids decision-making for application of fungicides. The initial results of the
689 application of LWM for managing the Botryosphaeria canker and blight of walnut were very
690 promising (Michailides et al. 2015).

691 *Forecast based on host phenology or vectors*

692 For hosts, which show a short period of peak susceptibility, the final level of the disease can
693 be estimated according to weather conditions and inoculum quantity during that period.
694 Consequently, fungicide treatments should be applied during this time. Working with apples,
695 Smith and Hendrix (1984) showed that applying a fungicide during the silver-tip stage, which
696 is the most susceptible to black rot caused by *D. seriata*, reduced five sprays of fungicides per
697 season to only one spray.

698 Finally, in the case of olive escudete, for which olive fly punctures are a prerequisite for
699 infection (Eldesouki-Arafat 2013; Moral et al. 2016), the disease forecast could be based on
700 risk models developed for olive fly (Ponti et al. 2014).

701 **DISEASE CONTROL**

702 Control of Botryosphaeriaceae species affecting perennial crops requires an integrated
703 approach (reviewed by Moral et al. 2019). Tree density and canopy management practices that
704 provide good ventilation and sunlight exposure decrease infection risk and symptom severity.
705 Pruning should eliminate dead tissues or affected ones bearing fruiting bodies of the pathogens
706 in order to reduce inoculum. Prunings left on the orchard ground, as well as almond stumps
707 left after removal of trees killed by band canker, should be eliminated by chipping or burning.

708 Irrigation practices minimize wetting of the trunk or canopy. In pistachio, Michailides and
709 Morgan (1993) reduced the incidence of blighted cluster from 92 to 21% using sprinklers of
710 low-trajectory angle, which minimized trunk and canopy wetting, rather than sprinklers with a
711 high-trajectory angle (Fig. 13). In the case of the almond LLDB disorder, the farmers should
712 avoid over-irrigation during the spring (Lampinen et al. 2009).

713 No almond, pistachio, or walnut cultivars are known to be completely resistant to species of
714 Botryosphaeriaeae, but some differences have been described. For example, the branches of
715 the common pistachio cvs. Kerman and Lost Hills are susceptible to the pathogen, whereas
716 their fruit show a high level of resistance to these species (Moral et al. 2019). The most
717 important differences have been described among olive cultivars. For example, cv. Gordal
718 Sevillana shows a marked susceptibility to *Neof. mediterraneum* under artificial and natural
719 infections (Moral et al. 2017a), as well as to escudete, in comparison with other cultivars
720 (Hojiblanca and Picual) under field conditions. Substantial cultivar differences of fruit
721 susceptibility to escudete have been described in Spain and Montenegro (Latinovic et al. 2013;
722 Moral et al. 2017a), although differences in cultivar attractiveness to olive fly could have an
723 important role in the percentage of diseased fruit.

724 In general, the use of different *Trichoderma* strains to control Botryosphaeriaceae species
725 affecting pistachio crop has failed (Michailides et al. 2005). However, other microbiological
726 control organisms, including yeast and bacteria, should be evaluated. Conversely, a good
727 number of different classes of synthetic fungicides, including some premixes of strobilurins
728 and carboxamides, have shown excellent efficacy in field conditions to control of pistachio
729 panicle and shoot blight (Adaskaveg et al. 2017). In this latter disease, spray applications
730 should be conducted at early bloom and be repeated in early summer (Michailides and Morgan
731 2004). However, for growers to be accurate and effective with the sprays, they can spray
732 according to advisories from the LWM model in pistachio and walnut orchards (Morgan et al.
733 2009). In the case of olive, fungicides should be applied after harvest, to protect the numerous
734 wounds caused by the harvesters, and at the end of the winter when it is frequent to find mature
735 ascospores (Moral et al. 2015; 2019). In the case of escudete, control of the olive fly is the most
736 efficient management measure against the fungal pathogen (Eldesouki-Arafat 2013). It should
737 be noted that the introduction of *P. berlesiana* as a predator of fly eggs in olive fly-free areas
738 could also suppress disease development.

Page | 24

739 CURRENT CHALLENGES AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

740 There are considerable challenges in advancing our knowledge of etiology of
741 Botryosphaeriaceae diseases affecting nut and olive crops, but less is known about their
742 epidemiology and ecology. Regarding etiology, interaction (competition, neutral, or
743 synergistic) among the various species in a given host has been scarcely studied. Such studies
744 could help us understand sign development and symptom expression on the tree. Although the
745 sexual state of certain members of Botryosphaeriaceae was found naturally occurring on
746 almond and walnut, in general, the role of sexual reproduction under field conditions has not
747 been studied. Methods for obtaining sexual fruiting bodies and ascospores of these species
748 could help us to understand this role and to characterize the type of sexual reproduction on the
749 members of this family. In growing areas where sexual stages are known, mating-type genes
750 (MAT) distribution is an excellent approach to understanding the equilibrium of the pathogen
751 population. There is a limited knowledge of the impact of Botryosphaeriaceae diseases on yield
752 and economic losses, although before the development of effective chemical control,
753 *Botryosphaeria* panicle and shoot blight of pistachio resulted in 100% crop loss in some
754 orchards. Standard protocols of stock plant management to avoid infected plant distribution,
755 ensuring the health plant status during the first years after plantation and pathogen spread, are
756 becoming ever more necessary considering the global movement of plant material. Advances

757 in our understanding of the “susceptibility window” of the different plant tissues (e.g.,
758 developing olive and walnut fruit(s) and growing walnut shoots) according to the dynamics of
759 antifungal compounds are essential to identify optimum time period for treatment. Similarly,
760 the impacts of biotic and abiotic stresses on plant predisposition to Botryosphaeriaceae species
761 and interactions with members of Diaporthaceae are crucial in understanding complex
762 situations, such as the decline of mature walnut orchards or LLDB of almond. Furthermore,
763 biotic stresses are clearly associated with a change of lifestyle of these species, but this
764 phenomenon has been little explored. In the case of almond band canker, members of
765 Botryosphaeriaceae transition from a saprophytic stage on the bark to a pathogenic stage in the
766 trunk wood. Clearly, a main challenge in research on olive “escudete” is how to identify when
767 female cecidomyiid flies acquire spores of *B. dothidea*. California pistachio and walnut
768 growers have benefited greatly by the use of the BUDMON and LWM for reducing the number
769 of fungicide applications while maintaining good control of Botryosphaeriaceae species on
770 both crops. However, LWM should be validated in other nut-growing areas before its use. The
771 development of robust mechanistic models that consider the different steps of the disease cycle
772 will help the process of validation in these areas. Finally, controlled studies on combining
773 cultural and chemical practices based on the dominant Botryosphaeriaceae species on each
774 nut/olive-producing area merits investigation for improving the management of Botryosphaeria
775 diseases.

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1127 **FIGURE LEGEND**

1128 **Figure 1.** Intensive pistachio (cv. Kerman), walnut (cv. Howard), and almond (cv. Nonpareil)
1129 plantations in California (**A, B & C**, respectively). Traditional almond plantation cv. Marcona
1130 under rainfall conditions in Southern Spain (**D**). Traditional multi-trunk olive cv. Hojiblanca
1131 tree in Southern Spain (**E**). Spain super-high density (hedgerow) olive plantation cv. Arbequina
1132 in Southern Spain (**D**)

Page | 33

1133 **Figure 2.** Articles on Botryosphaeriaceae species published in American Phytopathological
1134 Society Journals from 2000 to 2016, according to the topics of etiology, epidemiology/ecology,
1135 and control/resistance.

1136 **Figure 3.** Symptoms of Botryosphaeriaceae species affecting almond cv. Nonpareil: growth
1137 crack through which the pathogen infected the wood (**A**) and typical trunk gumming (**B**);
1138 blighted fruit (**C**), leading to canker formation (**D**).

1139 **Figure 4.** Symptoms of Botryosphaeriaceae species affecting olive cv. Gordal Sevillana.
1140 Typical “escudete” (= “small shield”) caused by *Botryosphaeria dothidea* in olive fruit (**A**).
1141 Mummified fruit infected by *B. dothidea* showing the original “escudete” symptom (**B**). Olive
1142 tree showing dieback of branches caused by *Neofusicoccum mediterraneum* (**C**)

1143 **Figure 5.** Symptoms of Botryosphaeriaceae species affecting pistachio and walnut. Pistachio
1144 cv. Kerman showing general blight of canopy (**A**). Infected fruit of pistachio cv. Kerman by
1145 *Neof. mediterraneum* (**B**). Walnut orchard cv. Vina showing dieback of branches (**C**). Fruit
1146 walnut cv. Chandler infected by Botryosphaeriaceae species (**D**)

1147 **Figure 6.** Pistachio yields (Kg/ha) in California from 1979 to 2017. Note the effects of the
1148 Botryosphaeria panicle and shoot blight epidemics (1995-1998), drought period (2012-2014),
1149 and low chilling hours during winter of 2014

1150 **Figure 7.** Hosts of Botryosphaeriaceae species growing contiguously, which allows cross-
1151 inoculum among them. Californian pistachio orchards close to riparian areas that serve as
1152 inoculum sources for the pathogen (**A & B**). Typical landscape with Botryosphaeriaceae host
1153 crops (olives and grapevines) in Southern Spain (**C**). Centenary olive tree growing in the center
1154 of a grape vineyard in Southern Spain (**D**)

1155 **Figure 8.** Fungal infection associated with pruning and harvest wounds. Colonization of
1156 almond trunk and scaffold branch (exuding sap) through pruning wounds by
1157 Botryosphaeriaceae spp. (**A & B**). Colonization of walnut shoot through pruning wound by
1158 *Neofusicoccum parvum* (**C**). Basidiomycete species associated with scaffold pruning cut in an
1159 olive tree (**D**). Basidiomycete species associated with damages caused by a trunk shaker in an
1160 olive tree cv. Picual (**E**)

1161 **Figure 9.** Disease cycles of Botryosphaeria panicle and shoot blight of pistachio,
1162 Botryosphaeria and Phomopsis canker and blight of walnut, and olive dieback of branches
1163 caused by *Neofusicoccum mediterraneum*.

1164 **Figure 10.** Relationship between distance (m) from inoculum source and the incidence or
1165 severity of symptoms of almond band canker caused by Botryosphaeriaceae species. Incidence
1166 of band canker in a third-leaf almond orchard at difference distances from an irrigation canal
1167 and the riparian vegetation providing the inoculum source of the pathogen (**A**). Relative
1168 severity of symptoms (%) and mortality (%) due to band canker in a fifth-leaf almond cv.
1169 Nonpareil orchard almond orchard as affected by distance from a walnut orchard that served
1170 as the inoculum source of the pathogen (**B**). The line represents the exponential models ($S =$

1171 $a \times b^D$) relating severity (S) of symptoms to distance (D) from the inoculum source. Dashed lines
1172 represent confidence intervals at 95%.

1173 **Figure 11.** Relative risk of infection of pistachio fruit by *Neofusicoccum mediterraneum* as
1174 determined by the wetness period (W) events and temperature (T). Wetness periods are
1175 calculated by combining ≤ 12 h of dry periods initiated by rain events with ≥ 4 mm of rain per
1176 event as recorded by electronic wetness sensors.

Page | 34

1177 **Figure 12.** Incidence of blighted clusters of pistachio caused by *Neofusicoccum mediterraneum*
1178 as affected by the grower's calendar-timed spray schedule (8 fungicide sprays per season), or
1179 according to the Leaf Wetness Model (2 fungicide sprays per season), and untreated control
1180 trees.

1181 **Figure 13.** Effect of irrigation using sprinklers with two different trajectory angles on the
1182 incidence of pistachio blighted clusters caused by *Neofusicoccum mediterraneum*. Means with
1183 different letters are significantly different according to Student's t-test at $P = 0.05$.

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TABLE 1. Virulence of Botryosphaeriaceae species affecting almond, pistachio, walnut, and olive

<i>Pathogen Species</i>	Host and Virulent					References
	Almond	Pistachio	Walnut	Olive		
				Branch	Fruit	
<i>Botryosphaeria dothidea</i>	MV ^a	MV	MV	WV	WV	Abdollahzadeh et al. 2013; Chen et al. 2014a; 2014b; Gramaje et al. 2012; Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Lazzizzera et al. 2008a; Lazzizzera et al. 2008b; Mohammadi et al. 2015; Moral et al. 2010; Phillips et al. 2005; Úrbez-Torres et al. 2013;
<i>Diplodia corticola</i>	-	-	-	WV	-	Romero, 2012.
<i>D. mutila</i>	- ^b	-	WV	MV	+	Chen et al. 2014a; Lazzizzera et al. 2008b; Úrbez-Torres et al. 2013
<i>D. olivarum</i>	WV	-	-	-	+	Gramaje et al. 2012; Lazzizzera et al. 2008b; Olmo 2015
<i>D. pinea</i>	-	-	-	-	+	Lazzizzera et al. 2008b
<i>D. scrobiculata</i>	-	-	-	-	+	Lazzizzera et al. 2008b
<i>D. seriata</i>	WV	WV	WV	WV	WV	Gramaje et al. 2012; Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Moral et al. 2008; 2010; Olmo, 2015; Úrbez-Torres et al. 2013
<i>Dothiorella iberica</i>	+	WV	WV	WV	-	Chen et al. 2014a; Doll et al. 2015; Úrbez-Torres et al. 2013
<i>Do. sarmentorum,</i>	WV	WV	-	-	-	Inderbitzin et al. 2010
<i>Do. viticola</i>	-	+	-	-	-	Mohammadi et al. 2015
<i>Lasiodiplodia americana</i>	-	MV	-	-	-	Chen et al. 2015
<i>L. citricola</i>	-	HV	HV ^c	-	-	Chen et al. 2014a
<i>L. gilanensis</i>	-	HV	-	-	-	Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Chen et al. 2014a
<i>L. theobromae</i>	MV	MV	+	WV	-	Chen et al. 2013a; Chen et al. 2013b; Haggag et al. 2007; Úrbez-Torres et al. 2013
<i>Macrophomina phaseolina</i>	MV	+	-	+ ^d	-	Chen et al. 2014b; Gramaje et al. 2012; Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Sergeeva et al. 2005
<i>Neofusicoccum australe</i>	+	+	-	-	MV	Armengol et al. 2008; Gramaje et al. 2012; Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Lazzizzera et al. 2008a
<i>Neof. hellenicum</i>	-	MV	-	-	-	Chen et al. 2015
<i>Neof. luteum</i>	HV	-	MV	WV	+	Martos, 2008; Olmo 2015; Sergeeva et al. 2009; Úrbez-Torres et al. 2013
<i>Neof. mediterraneum</i>	MV	MV	MV	HV	HV	Chen et al. 2014a; Moral et al. 2010; 2016; Úrbez-Torres et al. 2013
<i>Neof. nonquaesitum</i>	HV	-	MV	-	-	Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Chen et al. 2014a; 2014b
<i>Neof. parvum</i>	HV	HV	HV	MV	WV	Abdollahzadeh et al. 2013; Chen et al. 2014a; Carlucci et al. 2013; Chen et al. 2014a; Gramaje et al. 2012; Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Lazzizzera et al. 2008a; Martos, 2008; Mohammadi et al. 2015
<i>Neof. vitifusiforme</i>	+	MV	WV	WV	MV	Chen et al. 2014a; 2014b; Inderbitzin et al. 2010; Lazzizzera et al. 2008a; Úrbez-Torres et al. 2013
<i>Neoscytalidium dimidiatum</i>	+	+	MV ^c	-	-	Chen et al. 2014a

^aHighly, Moderately, and Weakly Virulent = HV, MV, and WV, respectively.

^bSpecies non-described = Species described but non-virulence test data to compare.

^cSpecies causing infection in graft union of walnut trees in commercial nurseries (Chen et al. 2014).

^dSpecies associated to root rot in young olive trees (Sanchez-Hernandez et al. 1998; Sergeeva et al. 2005) and young almond trees in California.

TABLE 2. Characteristics of diseases caused by Botryosphaeriaceae species affecting almond, pistachio, walnut, and olive

Host (species)	Disease	Main Pathogens (Total species)	Symptoms							Inoculum		Insect Role		Epidemiologist characteristics	Control
			Trunk	Branch	Gumming	Bud	Leaf	Fruit	Pycniospores	Ascospores	Vectors	Inductor			
Almond (<i>Prunus dulcis</i>)	Band canker (Canker of the trunk and scaffold branches)	<i>B. dothidea</i> , <i>Neof. parvum</i> , (13)	+++	+++	+++	-	-	-	+++	+	-	-	Mono or oligocyclic pathogen Polyetic epidemic	Irrigation management; timely pruning	
	Lower Limb Dieback	<i>B. dothidea</i> (2)	-	+++	-	-	-	-	+++	?	-	-	-	Irrigation management	
Pistachio (<i>Pistachia vera</i>)	Botryosphaeria panicle and shoot blight	<i>Neof. mediterraneum</i>	+	+++	-	++	+	++	+++	-*	-	<i>Thyanta pallidovirens</i> , <i>Acrosternum hilare</i> , <i>Leptoglossus clypealis</i> <i>Palumbina gerinii</i>	Mono or oligocyclic pathogen Polyetic epidemic	Irrigation management; Selective pruning; control of stinkbugs; Chemical sprays	
Walnut (<i>Juglans regia</i>)	Botryosphaeria canker and blight (Melaxuma)	<i>L. citricola</i> <i>Neof. parvum</i> (10)	+++ **	+++	-	+	-	++	+++	+	-	<i>Quadraspidiotus juglansregiae</i>	Mono or oligocyclic pathogen Polyetic epidemic	Selective pruning; Irrigation management; Control walnut scale; Chemical sprays	
Olive (<i>Olea europaea</i>)	Branch dieback	<i>Neof. mediterraneum</i> (20)	+	+++	-	-	-	+	+++	++	-	-	Mono or oligocyclic pathogen Polyetic epidemic	Selective pruning Cultivars different than 'Gordal sevillana' Chemical sprays	
	Escudete (Dalmatian disease)	<i>B. dothidea</i> (1)	-	-	-	-	-	+	+++	-	<i>Prolasiotera berlesiana</i>	<i>Bactrocera olea</i>	Interaction fly-mosquito-fungus	Control olive fly (<i>Bactrocera oleae</i>) Cultivar resistance	

Figure 1. Intensive pistachio (cv. Kerman), walnut (cv. Howard), and almond (cv. Nonpareil) plantations in California (A, B & C, respectively). Traditional almond plantation cv. Marcona under rainfall conditions in Southern Spain (D). Traditional multi-trunk olive cv. Hojiblanca tree in Southern Spain (E). Spain super-high density (hedgerow) olive plantation cv. Arbequina in Southern Spain (D).

190x338mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 2. Articles on Botryosphaeriaceae species published in American Phytopathological Society Journals from 2000 to 2016, according to the topics of etiology, epidemiology/ecology, and control/resistance.

190x338mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 3. Symptoms of Botryosphaeriaceae species affecting almond cv. Nonpareil: growth crack through which the pathogen infected the wood (A) and typical trunk gumming (B); blighted fruit (C), leading to canker formation (D).

190x338mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 4. Symptoms of Botryosphaeriaceae species affecting olive cv. Gordal Sevillana. Typical “escudete” (= “small shield”) caused by *Botryosphaeria dothidea* in olive fruit (A). Mummified fruit infected by *B. dothidea* showing the original “escudete” symptom (B). Olive tree showing dieback of branches caused by *Neofusicoccum mediterraneum* (C).

190x338mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 5. Symptoms of Botryosphaeriaceae species affecting pistachio and walnut. Pistachio cv. Kerman showing general blight of canopy (A). Infected fruit of pistachio cv. Kerman by *Neof. mediterraneum* (B). Walnut orchard cv. Vina showing dieback of branches (C). Fruit walnut cv. Chandler infected by Botryosphaeriaceae species (D).

190x338mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 6. Pistachio yields (Kg/ha) in California from 1979 to 2017. Note the effects of the Botryosphaeria panicle and shoot blight epidemics (1995-1998), drought period (2012-2014), and low chilling hours during winter of 2014.

190x338mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 7. Hosts of Botryosphaeriaceae species growing contiguously, which allows cross-inoculum among them. Californian pistachio orchards close to riparian areas that serve as inoculum sources for the pathogen (A & B). Typical landscape with Botryosphaeriaceae host crops (olives and grapevines) in Southern Spain (C). Centenary olive tree growing in the center of a grape vineyard in Southern Spain (D).

190x338mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 8. Fungal infection associated with pruning and harvest wounds. Colonization of almond trunk and scaffold branch (exuding sap) through pruning wounds by *Botryosphaeriaceae* spp. (A & B). Colonization of walnut shoot through pruning wound by *Neofusicoccum parvum* (C). Basidiomycete species associated with scaffold pruning cut in an olive tree (D). Basidiomycete species associated with damages caused by a trunk shaker in an olive tree cv. Picual (E).

190x338mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 9. Disease cycles of Botryosphaeria panicle and shoot blight of pistachio, Botryosphaeria and Phomopsis canker and blight of walnut, and olive dieback of branches caused by Neofusicoccum mediterraneum.

254x190mm (100 x 100 DPI)

Figure 10. Relationship between distance (m) from inoculum source and the incidence or severity of symptoms of almond band canker caused by *Botryosphaeriaceae* species. Incidence of band canker in a third-leaf almond orchard at difference distances from an irrigation canal and the riparian vegetation providing the inoculum source of the pathogen (A). Relative severity of symptoms (%) and mortality (%) due to band canker in a fifth-leaf almond cv. Nonpareil orchard almond orchard as affected by distance from a walnut orchard that served as the inoculum source of the pathogen (B). The line represents the exponential models ($S = a \times b^D$) relating severity (S) of symptoms to distance (D) from the inoculum source. Dashed lines represent confidence intervals at 95%.

190x338mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 11. Relative risk of infection of pistachio fruit by *Neofusicoccum mediterraneum* as determined by the wetness period (W) events and temperature (T). Wetness periods are calculated by combining ≤ 12 h of dry periods initiated by rain events with ≥ 4 mm of rain per event as recorded by electronic wetness sensors.

190x338mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 12. Incidence of blighted clusters of pistachio caused by *Neofusicoccum mediterraneum* as affected by the grower's calendar-timed spray schedule (8 fungicide sprays per season), or according to the Leaf Wetness Model (2 fungicide sprays per season), and untreated control trees.

190x338mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 13. Effect of irrigation using sprinklers with two different trajectory angles on the incidence of pistachio blighted clusters caused by *Neofusicoccum mediterraneum*. Means with different letters are significantly different according to Student's t-test at P = 0.05.

190x338mm (96 x 96 DPI)